

Tensile and Compressive Deformation and Fracture Behavior of the Al-Al₃Ni Eutectic Composites at Elevated Temperatures

O. Yanagisawa¹⁾, T. Yano²⁾

- 1) Faculty of Engineering, Hiroshima University, Saijo-Shitami, Higashi-Hiroshima City, 724, Japan
- 2) Student of Graduate School, Hiroshima University, Saijo-Shitami, Higashi-Hiroshima City, 724, Japan

ABSTRACT

Experimental results of the temperature and strain rate dependences of ultimate tensile and compressive strength and deformation modes of unidirectionally solidified Al-Al₃Ni eutectic composites are presented. The importance of accumulative fiber breaking is emphasized especially in tensile deformation and fracture.

INTRODUCTION

Unidirectionally solidified eutectic composites are promising as the materials for use at high temperatures since each phase of them is thermally stable (1,2). It has been found that the tensile strength of an Al-Al₃Ni eutectic composite at $T=743\text{K}$ and $\dot{\epsilon}=2.1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ is about 1/4 of that at room temperature (R.T.) and the nominal stress falls down gradually after the maximum load in the stress-strain curve. The fracture surface of this specimen does not have a typical dimple pattern with nucleus of each fiber but has broken fibers on the fracture surface of matrix. B.Cantor et al (3) interpreted that the pull-out of fibers controls the tensile strength. Fracture surface obtained by a high temperature creep rupture test has a dimple pattern which is bigger than that pulled at R.T. (4). These results suggest that the tensile deformation and fracture behaviors of the composites at elevated temperatures depend on the mechanical stability of fibers.

Tensile strength of Al-Al₃Ni eutectic composite at R.T. is generally represented by the mixture rule or the modified mixture rule considering accumulative fracture of fibers (5, 6, 7). Accumulative fracture of fibers related to the mechanical stability may be important particularly at high temperatures. In this study, temperature and strain rate dependences of tensile and compressive deformation and fracture behaviors of unidirectionally solidified Al-Al₃Ni eutectic composites without cell structure were examined to investigate the mechanical stability of the fibers at elevated temperatures.

MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENT

A master alloy of Al-6.13 mass% Ni eutectic composition was prepared by melting 99.99%Al and 99.9%Ni and casting into a metal mold. Machined $\phi 8 \times 90$ mm rods of the master alloy were unidirectionally solidified in graphite crucibles by the Bridgeman method with the solidification rate of 35 mm/h and the temperature

Fig.1 Microstructure of Al-Al₃Ni eutectic composite.
 (a) Transverse section (b) Longitudinal section

gradient of about 6 K/mm. Microstructures of specimens are shown in Fig.1, from which it is known that this material has a eutectic structure of single crystal matrix without cell structure. The specimens of $\phi 4 \times 18$ mm gauge length for tension and 10×10 mm for compression were tested at the temperatures $T = R.T. \sim 773$ K and at the strain rates $\dot{\epsilon} = 9.3 \times 10^{-6} \sim 9.3 \times 10^{-3} s^{-1}$.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tensile Tests

Fig.2 shows some examples of the nominal stress-crosshead displacement curves for tensile tests at R.T. and 673K. Shapes of the curves are classified into two groups, (i) in which loads drop abruptly after the maximum load and their fracture strain is very small and (ii) in which loads fall off gradually after the maximum load and their fracture strain is very large. Fig.3 is a typical example of (ii) in which true stress decreases slightly after the maximum load and then the deformation proceeds with a constant true stress to the true strain of rupture of about 200%.

As shown in Fig.4 of ultimate tensile strength (U.T.S.)-strain rate/temperature relationship, U.T.S. at 473K, 573K, 673K and 773K rises with increasing

Fig.2 Nominal stress-crosshead displacement curves of tensile tests, gauge length=18 mm. (a)293K, (b)673K

strain rate, though the strength at R.T. is remained constant. Fractographies of these specimens were classified into two groups. The specimens fractured at low temperature-high strain rate have dimple patterns similar to those at R.T. and the specimens at high temperature-low strain rate have larger dimple patterns with fragments of broken fibers as reported in the previous papers (4). These two kinds of fracture surface correspond to the two regions divided by a dotted line in Fig.4 and also to the abovementioned two types of stress-displacement curves (i), (ii).

Fig.5 shows crack initiation (a) observed in the specimen unloaded at about maximum load after being pulled at $T=623\text{K}$ and $\dot{\epsilon}=1.9\times 10^{-3}\text{S}^{-1}$ in region (i) and shear deformation bands (b) observed on the polished surface of the specimen pulled beyond the maximum load at $T=773\text{K}$ and $\dot{\epsilon}=9.3\times 10^{-4}\text{S}^{-1}$ in region (ii) and unloaded at about 60% of U.T.S.. The macroscopic feature of fracture changes from a shear type under the condition in region (i) and in region (ii) very near to the dotted line to a cup and cup type under the condition in (ii) far from the dotted line of Fig.4.

Accumulative fiber fracture has been observed in tensile deformation even at R.T. according to C. Baromeo et al (6). Probability of fiber breaking depending on temperature and strain rate was measured also in this study. Fig.6 shows the density of fiber breaks b at $T=473\text{K}$, 773K and $\dot{\epsilon}=9.26\times 10^{-4}\text{S}^{-1}$, $1.85\times 10^{-5}\text{S}^{-1}$. Here the values b at zero stress of composites mean the densities of fiber breaks which occur in whole process excepting a loading (heating before loading and cooling, mechanical cutting, mechanical polishing and chemical etching of specimens after loading). Density of fiber breaks at a given stress increases as the strain rate decreases at both temperatures. Fig.5 also shows that the tendency of fiber breaking becomes greater with temperature rising at the smaller strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}=1.85\times 10^{-5}\text{S}^{-1}$. From these results, the effects of strain rate and temperature on the tensile deformation and fracture behaviors seemed to be related to those of strain rate and temperature on the accumulative fracture of fibers.

Fig.3 True stress-true strain curve at $T=773\text{K}$, $\dot{\epsilon}=9.3\times 10^{-5}\text{S}^{-1}$.

Fig.4 Variation of ultimate tensile strength (U.T.S.) with strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon}$).

Fig.5 Crack initiation (a) ($T=623\text{K}$, $\dot{\epsilon}=1.9 \times 10^{-3}\text{S}^{-1}$) and shear deformation band formation (b) ($T=773\text{K}$, $\dot{\epsilon}=9.3 \times 10^{-4}\text{S}^{-1}$).

Compressive Tests

Fig.7 shows some examples of the nominal stress-crosshead displacement curves in compression tests. Beyond the maximum load, the load falls down and goes up again and repeats this process. Displacement until the maximum load at which buckling occurs decreases as temperature rises or strain rate decreases.

As shown in Fig.8 of ultimate compressive strength (U.C.S.)- strain rate/temperature relationship, U.C.S. rises with increasing strain rate at 473K, 673K and 773K, though the strength is constant at R.T. independently of strain rate. The macroscopic feature of the specimens compressed at $\dot{\epsilon}=8.33 \times 10^{-5}\text{S}^{-1}$ is shown in Fig.9. The morphology of buckling at 473K is interesting, which shows a "multiple kinking" with many small kink bands. B.W. Rosen (8) predicted the two buckling modes of fibers in compressive deformation, an extension mode and a shear mode, but only the shear mode buckling was observed in this study.

Fig.6 Density of fiber breaks (b) at various nominal stresses of composite.

Fig.7 Nominal stress-crosshead displacement curves of compressive tests, gauge length=10 mm.
 (a) 293K, (b) 673K

Fig.8 Variation of ultimate compressive strength (U.C.S.) with strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon}$)

Fig.9 Macroscopic morphology of compressed specimens.
 $\dot{\epsilon}=8.33 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$

Fig.10 Microscopic morphology of kink deformation bands. (a), (b) Surface (c) Longitudinal section

SUMMARY

The temperature and strain rate dependences of tensile and compressive deformation and fracture of unidirectionally solidified Al-Al₃Ni eutectic composites without cell structure were investigated. In tensile tests, the accumulative fracture or the multiple internal fracture of fibers followed by the crack formation decides U.T.S. at low temperatures and high strain rates and the multiple internal fracture of fibers followed by the formation of shear deformation band decides U.T.S. at high temperatures and low strain rates. Therefore the dependences of U.T.S. on temperature and strain rate must be influenced by the dependence of fiber breaking on them.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are indebted to Prof. Dr. M. Ohmori, Faculty of Engineering of Hiroshima University, for his helpful discussion.

REFERENCES

- 1 Y.Nakagawa, A.Ohtomo, Y.Saiga, "Directional Solidification of Superalloys" , Bulletin of J.I.M., 17(1978), pp.589
- 2 K.Maruyama, "High Temperature Creep of Directionally Solidified Eutectic Composites", Bulletin of J.I.M., 20(1981), pp.106
- 3 B.Cantor, G.J.May and G.A.Chadwick, "The tensile fracture behavior of the aligned Al-Al₃Ni and Al-CuAl₂ eutectics at various temperatures", J.Mater.Sci., 8(1973), pp.830
- 4 E.M.Breinan, E.R.Thompson, G.P.Mccarthy and W.J.Herman, "Microstructural Characteristics of the Directionally-Solidified Al-Al₃Ni Eutectic and Their Influence on Creep Fracture, Met. Trans., 3(1972), pp.221
- 5 R.W.Hertzberg, F.D.Lemkey and J.A.Ford, "Mechanical Behavior of Lamellar (Al-CuAl₂) and Wisker Type (Al-Al₃Ni)Unidirectionally-Solidified Eutectic Alloys" , Trans.AIME, 233(1965), pp.342
- 6 C.Baromeo and T.H.Courtney, "Partitioning of Stress Between Fiber and Matrix During Tensile Deformation of the Al-Al₃Ni Eutectic Composite", Met.Trans. , 4(1973), pp.1821
- 7 B.Cantor and G.A.Chadwick, "The tensile deformation of unidirectionally solidified Al-Al₃Ni and Al-Al₂Cu eutectics", J. Mater.Sci., 10(1975), pp.578
- 8 B.W.Rosen, Fiber Composites Mater. Am.Soc. Metals., 1965, pp.37